

Pythagoras' Theorem, Scaling and $X \rightarrow -X, Y \rightarrow -Y$

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Pythagoras' theorem may be readily derived using linear algebra and the notion of rotations. In such a case, one has the rotationally invariant modulus $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. There seems, however, to be an interest in the geometric interpretation of the sum of areas of squares linked with the hypotenuse r , and the two sides x, y . Here we try to consider obtaining the Pythagoras' theorem without starting with the notion of rotational invariance. In particular, we focus on scaling. If one does not enforce rotational invariance, it seems one may restrict x and y to the first quadrant and call $-x$ and $-y$ values unphysical. In such a case, one only has scaling to rely on. For $y=0$, $r=x$ and for $x=0$, $r=y$. Employing scaling would at first lead to a trial of $r=x+y$. This implies that for a 45 degree angle, $x=.5r$ and $y=.5r$, but this, as we show, cannot be due to properties of a circle. Thus, the linear form is not suitable. We next consider describing the problem in terms of an angle. In such a case, there is no longer a physical objection to $-x$ and $-y$ and it seems that there is no reason to restrict the angle to the range 0, 90 degrees. In fact, this viewpoint seems to suggest that an equation $r(x,y)$ should include all values of x, y , i.e. positive and negative. (In other words, rotational invariance seems to be present whether one introduces it a priori or not.) Thus, one requires a $r(x,y)$ which scales and is even. Due to scaling, one can only have x to a single even power and y to the same even power. The task is then to show that this even power must be 2 and not a higher even number. We argue that this may be done by considering properties of the angle viewpoint. This, then brings in the geometrical interpretation of the area of a square.

Pythagoras' Theorem and Rotational Invariance

One may readily derive Pythagoras' theorem using linear algebra and the notion of a modulus (dot product of r vector dot r vector) which is invariant under rotations, i.e.

$$r \text{ vector dot } r \text{ vector} = \text{invariant} = x^2 + y^2 = r^2 \quad ((1))$$

Given that linear algebra was developed centuries after Pythagoras' theorem and that the focus is usually on the geometric notion of r, x and y representing areas of squares, we try to obtain the Pythagoras' theorem without using linear algebra and an a priori notion of rotational invariance.

Scaling

We first consider triangles that exist in the first quadrant as we are not interested in rotational invariance. In such a case, we exclude negative values of x and y . We seek $r(x,y)$. As a first step, we argue that one may change the units used to measure r, x, y which means that the formula $r(x,y)$ must obey scaling, which we argue is key. For:

$$x=0 \quad r=y \quad \text{and for } y=0 \quad r=x \quad ((2))$$

If $r(x,y)$ contains functions like $\exp(x/a)$ etc then such a function does not scale and there does not seem to be any natural parameters like "a" in the problem. We consider the simplest situation:

$$r = x + y \quad ((3))$$

The problem with ((3)) is that for a 45 degree angle, one expects $x=.5r$ and $y=.5r$. If one considers r as the radius of a circle, then for $y=0$, $r=x$. If $x=.5r$, then a vertical line from this point does not seem to intersect the end of the radius vector which makes a 45 degree angle. Thus, ((3)) must be rejected and some other power of x and y introduced. Due to scaling, one may only have a single power of x and y . The question then arises as to whether one may have cross terms like x power a y power b . This will also have to be addressed.

Thinking in Terms of Angles

Given $r(x,y)$, with r being the radius of a circle, for a given r,x,y set in the first quadrant, one may create an infinite number of right angle triangles, all with the same angle between r and the x axis. The angle defines all of these triangles, i.e. one may consider r/r , x/r and y/r as all defining the same angle. In such a case, a restriction to the first quadrant (due to the argument that $-x$ and $-y$ are unphysical) is problematic because there is no reason to restrict the angle θ . It simply describes triangles with different orientations (which is also what $x,-y$, $-x,y$ and $-x,-y$ do). As a result, a more general description is one in which all quadrants are involved and this forces the single power of x and y to be even. Furthermore, if the single power is 2, one cannot have the cross term xy because it takes on different values in different quadrants. In other words, even if one does not wish to consider rotational invariance, it is present.

It is possible to determine some features of the angular viewpoint. First:

$$f(\theta) = x/r \quad \text{and} \quad g(\theta) = y/r \quad \text{where } f \text{ and } g \text{ are unknown functions} \quad ((4))$$

Both f and g are periodic functions if one considers all four quadrants.

Here θ is the angle between r and x . Then, the angle between y and r is $90-\theta$ and:

$$x = r g(90 - \theta) \quad \text{and} \quad y = r f(90-\theta) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{So: } f(\theta) = g(90-\theta) \quad \text{and} \quad g(\theta) = f(90-\theta) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{From } ((4)) \quad f(\theta) = 1 \text{ and } g(\theta) = 0 \quad \text{for } \theta = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad f(90 \text{ degrees}) = 0, \quad g(90 \text{ degrees}) = 1 \quad ((7))$$

We argue that ((7)) is consistent with:

$$f(a+b) = f(a)f(b) - g(a)g(b) \quad \text{and} \quad g(a+b) = g(a)f(b) + f(a)g(b) \quad ((8))$$

for $\theta=0$ and $\theta = 90$ degrees. One might argue that introducing powers of f and g are also consistent for $\theta=0$, and $\theta=90$, but this would involve introducing the powers in an asymmetric manner which would treat a and b differently. Thus, we suggest that one consider ((8)). The main reason we focus on ((8)) is that we are interested in derivatives of f and g .

If one considers $a=b=\theta=q$, then:

$$d/d q f(2q) = 2 f(q) df(q)/dq - 2 g(q) dg(q)/dq \quad ((9a))$$

If $df(q)/dq = -g(q)$ and $dg(q)/dq = f(q)$ ((10)),

then one has consistency with $f(2q)$ and $g(2q)$.

This, however, points to the single power associated with x and y as being 2 because then:

$$1 = f(q)f(q) + g(q)g(q) \text{ i.e. } 0 = f df/dq + g dg/dq \text{ which matches ((10)).}$$

Thus, it is the quadratic form of rr , xx , and yy which allows for scaling and $x \rightarrow -x$, $y \rightarrow -y$ and this quadratic form has the geometric area of a square.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one does not wish to use linear algebra to derive Pythagoras' theorem, one may use scaling and the notion of $x \rightarrow -x$ and $y \rightarrow -y$ leaving $r(x,y)$ invariant. This approach requires one to go beyond the first quadrant and this seems to be linked to a θ based treatment of the problem, where θ is the angle between r and the x axis.